

**PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF CHEMICAL INTERACTION AND GLASS
FORMATION IN THE TlAsSe₂-InSe SYSTEM**

Gashimov Kh.

Ph.D., Associate Prof.,

Azerbaijan State Economic University

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Abstract

Using physicochemical methods of analysis: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as by measuring density and microhardness, chemical interactions and glass formation in the TlAsSe₂-InSe system were studied and a T-x phase diagram was constructed. It has been established that the phase diagram of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system is a quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary Tl₂Se-As₂Se₃-InSe system and is eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed between the TlAsSe₂ and InSe compounds in the system is 20 mol % InSe, temperature 170°C. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on TlAsSe₂ reach 5 mol % InSe, and solid solutions based on InSe amount to 2.5 mol % TlAsSe₂. The glass formation regions based on TlAsSe₂ extend up to 20 mol % InSe.

Keywords: glass formation, quasi-binary, eutectic, microhardness, phase diagram.

Introduction

The TlAsSe₂ component included in the TlAsSe₂-InSe system is obtained from the As₂Se₃ and Tl₂Se compounds. These components that made up the system were materials with functional properties. Arsenic chalcogenides are widely used as photosensitive [1-5] and luminescent [6,7] materials in optical systems. In recent years, glassy chalcogenide fibers based on arsenic chalcogenides have found application as a compact nonlinear medium providing efficient Romanov amplification and lasing, pulse compression, optical regeneration, and wavelength conversion [8–10]. Thallium compounds with ternary chalcogenide phases obtained on their basis are photosensitive semiconductors in the visible region of the spectrum [11,12]. The InSe compound, its ternary compounds and solid solutions are semiconductor materials with photosensitive and thermoelectric properties [13,14]. Many systems consisting of arsenic chalcogenides have been studied in the literature [15–20]. From this point of view, alloys of complex composition obtained by chemical interaction of TlAsSe₂ and InSe compounds can also be photosensitive materials.

The TlAsSe₂ compound melts congruently at 265°C, its microhardness is 920 MPa, T_g=100°C [21]. The InSe compound melts congruently at 660°C and crystallizes in the hexagonal syngony, lattice parameter: $a = 0.405$ nm, $c = 1.693$ nm, space gr. P63/mmc has a density of 5.56 g/cm³ [22].

Experimental part

Alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system were synthesized from the TlAsSe₂ and InSe components by co-melting in quartz ampoules, evacuated to a pressure of

0.133 Pa in the temperature range 500–800°C. To bring the alloys to equilibrium, they were subjected to heat treatment at a temperature of 170°C for 350 hours. Then the alloys of the system were studied by DTA, X-ray diffraction analysis, MSA, density and microhardness measurements.

Differential thermal analysis was carried out using a TERMOSCAN-2 device. The heating rate of the alloys was 5 degrees/min. Chromel-alumel was used as a thermocouple.

X-ray phase analysis of the alloys was carried out on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. A CuK α electrode was used as an irradiator. Microhardness was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic microscope. Microstructure analysis was carried out using a MIM-8 microscope. When determining the densities of the system alloys, the pycnometric method was used and toluene was used as a filling solution.

Results and its discussion

In the TlAsSe₂-InSe system, alloys obtained in the range of 0–20 mol % InSe is glassy, and the remaining alloys are dark gray substances obtained in the form of crystals. During the differential thermal analysis of the alloys, it was established that two endothermic effects are observed in the thermograms of the samples. It has been established that in the thermograms of alloys in the concentration range of 0–20 mol % InSe has a softening temperature T_g = 100°C, characteristic of glasses. When studying the microstructure of alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system, single- and two-phase regions were discovered. In Fig. 1 shows the microstructures of alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system with a content of 5, 60 and 97.5 mol % InSe.

*Figure 1. Microstructures of TlAsSe₂-InSe system alloys.
1-5 mol %, 2-60 mol %, 3-97.5 mol % InSe.*

As can be seen from the microstructure, single-phase samples 5 and 97.5 mol % InSe are solid solution alloys based on TlAsSe_2 and InSe compounds, respectively. Sample 60 mol % InSe is a two-phase field alloy.

To clarify the results of microstructural and differential thermal analysis, X-ray phase analysis of alloys containing 5, 10, 20, 60 and 97.5 mol % InSe (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys of the TlAsSe_2 -InSe system. 1- TlAsSe_2 , 2-5, 3-10, 4-20, 5-93 mol %, 6-100 mol % InSe.

Fig. 3. T - x phase diagram of the TlAsSe_2 -InSe system.

It was found that samples containing 5, 10, 20 mol % InSe are glassy. Existing diffraction lines in the diffraction pattern of the 60 mol % InSe alloy is a mixture of diffraction lines of TlAsSe_2 and InSe compounds, that is, it is a two-phase alloy. Diffraction lines of a sample containing 97.5 mol % InSe are identical to the diffraction lines of the InSe compound, that is, they are solid solutions based on InSe. The T - x phase diagram of the TlAsSe_2 -InSe system was constructed based on the results of physicochemical analysis methods (Fig.

3). The TlAsSe_2 -InSe system is quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed between the TlAsSe_2 and InSe compounds is 20 mol % InSe, temperature 170°C. In a system at room temperature, the region of solid solution based on the TlAsSe_2 compound is 5 mol % InSe, and the base InSe is up to 2.5 mol % TlAsSe_2 . In the TlAsSe_2 -InSe system, upon slow cooling based on TlAsSe_2 , the glass transition regions expand to 20 mol % InSe.

liquidus of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system consists of the primary crystallization curves of an α -solid solution based on the TlAsSe₂ compound and a β -solid solution based on InSe. Two-phase alloys consisting of (α + β) crystallize below the solidus line in the system.

When measuring the microhardness of alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system, two different values were obtained. The microhardness of α -solid solutions obtained

based on the TlAsSe₂ compound varies within the range (920-1050) MPa. The microhardness of β -solid solutions based on the InSe compound varies within the range (600-680) MPa. Table 1 shows some physico-chemical properties of alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system after heat treatment.

Table 1.

Composition of alloys of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system, results of DTA, density and microhardness measurements.

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, °C	Density, q/cm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
TlAsSe ₂	InSe			δ	α
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15 N
100	0.0	265	7,45	920	–
97	3,0	225,265	7,46	1050	–
95	5,0	200,250	7,40	1050	–
90	10	170,240	7,27	–	–
80	20	170	7,07	Eutek.	Eutek.
70	30	170,275	6,88	–	–
60	40	170,370	6,66	–	680
50	50	170,440	6,50	–	680
40	60	170,510	6,32	–	680
30	70	170,560	6,12	–	680
20	80	170,600	5,94	–	680
10	90	170,625	5,74	–	680
5,0	95	410,650	5,65	–	670
0,0	100	660	5,56	–	600

Conclusion

The T-x phase diagram of the TlAsSe₂-InSe system was constructed based on the results of physico-chemical analyses. The phase diagram of the system is quasi-binary, eutectic type. Cocrystallization of TlAsSe₂ and InSe compounds ends at the double eutectic point of composition 20 mol % InSe, temperature 170°C. In the TlAsSe₂-InSe system at room temperature, solid solutions based on the TlAsSe₂ compound reach 5 mol % InSe, and based on InSe compounds - up to 2.5 mol % TlAsSe₂. In the TlAsSe₂-InSe system, upon slow cooling based on the TlAsSe₂ compound, the glass transition region expands to 20 mol % InSe.

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